

SANSA Eastern Cape surveys: A checklist of the spiders (Arachnida, Araneae) of Thyspunt, South Africa

Ansie S. Dippenaar-Schoeman¹ & Linda Wiese²

¹Department of Zoology, University of Venda, South Africa, dippenaaransie@gmail.com

²South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA) Team, Eastern Cape, Jeffrey's Bay, South Africa, lwiese9@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), several surveys were undertaken in the Eastern Cape and this paper provides the first annotated species list of spiders presently known from Thyspunt, a small area in the Eastern Cape, marked for a possible nuclear installation. A total of 94 species from 75 genera and 26 families were recorded. The most species-rich families are the Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (19 spp.) and Thomisidae (15 spp.). The conservation status and level of endemism based on their known distribution are provided for each species.

Keywords: South African National Survey of Arachnida, Western Cape, conservation assessment

INTRODUCTION

During the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSA), 195 sites were sampled in the Eastern Cape but large areas have not been sampled yet. A total of 837 species, 38.6% of all South African species, have been recorded from the province (Dippenaar-Schoeman & Haddad, 2006; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). From the Eastern Cape, 23 protected areas have been sampled, mainly reserves, but also two national parks and state forest areas. In 13 of these areas, >50 specimens were sampled. The Mountain Zebra National Park was the first national park for which a species list was published (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988), with a subsequent update (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2006). The second national park that was surveyed in the province was the Addo Elephant National Park (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020). Other published surveys include the Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011) and Silaka Nature Reserve (Forbanka & Niba, 2013). In the Asante Sana Nature Reserve in the Sneeuwberg Mountains, a long survey formed part of a PhD study (Midgley, 2012), looking at the structure of epigeic invertebrate communities along an altitudinal gradient. Staff and students of the University of the Free State have done extensive sampling in the Amatola Mountains in the Hogsback area, while the University of KwaZulu-Natal was involved in sampling in the Mkambathi Nature Reserve (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011).

Other studies include behavioural studies on the subsocial eresid *Stegodyphus tentoriicola* Purcell, found in the Mountain Zebra National Park (Ruch *et al.*, 2009; 2012), while Wiese and Dippenaar-Schoeman (2021) reported on the pisaurid *Walrencea globosa* Blandin from Thyspunt.

This paper presents the first information on the spider fauna of Thyspunt, a small area in the Eastern Cape. Information on endemism and conservation status for 94 species is provided.

METHODS

Study area: Thyspunt (-34.1918°S; 24.7134°E) is a rocky stretch of coast just west of the Thysbaai beach. It is situated in a pristine 3 800-ha coastal site 5 km east of Oyster Bay and 12 km west of Cape St Francis and 17.3 km south of Humansdorp in the Eastern Cape (Fig. 1).

The site has an elevation of 12 m. The area is controversially earmarked by Eskom for the possible building of a 4 000-MW nuclear power station. It is defined by UNESCO as a "cultural landscape", as it has unique natural, historical and cultural qualities, and spiritual meaning for the local Khoekhoe and San community. Rare fynbos is endemic to the area. Thyspunt has unique vegetation – St Francis Fynbos / Thicket Mosaic – which only occurs between Huisclip (near Oyster Bay) to the west and Cape Recife (Gqeberha) to the east, and nowhere else in the world. Over 60% has been transformed by urbanisation, agriculture, forestry and alien plant invasions and it is severely threatened. It falls within the Cape Floral Kingdom, which is recognised as a biodiversity hotspot of global importance and is also an endemic bird area. In the Thyspunt thickets, there are protected trees such as *Sideroxylon inerme* (white milkwood) and *Pittosporum viridiflorum* (cheesewood). There are several plants at Thyspunt that are of conservation concern and that are listed on the Red List of South African Plants.

Sampling methods and identification: Sampling was done by the second author (LW) on the following dates: 19, 26, and 28 October 2011; 17 December 2011; 9 February 2012; 21 March 2012 and 4 April 2012. She used the following collecting methods: active search, beating, leaf litter, and sweeping.

Specimens were photographed and preserved in 70% ethanol. Identifications were done in Pretoria by the first author (AS). Some of the specimens could not be identified to species level because only immature specimens were sampled or the taxonomy of some families is still unresolved.

Voucher specimens: Specimens were deposited in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Council Plant Health and Protection in Pretoria.

Endemism value and conservation status: Detailed explanation of the indices to assess the endemism value and conservation status of each species can be found at the end of Appendix 1. It distinguishes between species only known from the type locality (6), the Eastern Cape (5), two adjoining provinces (4), South Africa (3), Southern Africa (2), Afrotropical Region (1), and finally areas outside the Afrotropical Region (0). The conservation status was derived from a recent National Red List assessment of spiders in South Africa.

Figures 1-4. Thyspunt: 1. Showing the vegetation types in Thyspunt; 2. *Pelargonium suburbanum* subsp. *suburbanum*; 3. *Agathosma stenopetala*; 4. *Capeochloa cincta* subsp. *sericea*. Photo credit Linda Wieses 2-4 Caryl Logie.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Numbers present: In total, 94 species in 75 genera and 26 families were recorded (see Table 1; Appendix 1). Ten could not be identified to species level as they are probably new or still immature. Unfortunately, some of them belong to large families that require comprehensive revision to determine the taxonomic status and identity of these taxa.

Family diversity: Of the 26 spider families collected from Thyspunt (see Table 1; Appendix 1), the Salticidae (19 spp.), Araneidae (19 spp.) and Thomisidae (15 spp.) are the most species-rich families. In the Mkambathi Nature Reserve, the Theridiidae and Araneidae were the most species-rich families (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2011), and at the Mountain Zebra National Park, it was the Thomisidae (Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1988; 2006), while at the Addo Elephant National Park, the Thomisidae (39 spp.), Araneidae (39 spp.), Salticidae (35 spp.) and Theridiidae (25 spp.) were the most species-rich families (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2020).

Species endemism: Of the 94 species sampled, only three species – *Neriene flammea* Van Helsdingen, 1969 (Linyphiidae), *Walrencea globosa* Blandin, 1979 (Pisauridae) and *Habrocestum laurae* Peckham and Peckham, 1903 (Pisauridae) – are data deficient (DD). Species of the families Araneidae (Fig. 7), Dictynidae (Fig. 11), Philodromidae (Fig. 16) and Theridiidae (Figs 26, 27) were not evaluated (NE) due to the taxonomic resolution of the respective genera. Seven of these species are possibly new to science.

Six species have a wide distribution and were possibly introduced to Africa. This includes several cosmopolitan species of the families Araneidae (*Cyclosa insulana*, *C. oculata*, *Cyrtophora citricola*, *Larinia chloris* and *Zygiella x-notata*) and two Theridiidae species (*Euryopsis funebris* and *Phycosoma martiniae*).

Table 1: Spider diversity of Thyspunt with the total number of families, genera and species sampled

Family	Gen.	Spp.	Family	Gen.	Spp.
Amaurobiidae	1	1	Palpimanidae	1	1
Araneidae	16	19	Philodromidae	2	2
Cheiracanthiidae	1	1	Pisauridae	3	3
Clubionidae	1	2	Salticidae	13	19
Corinnidae	1	1	Scytodidae	1	1
Cyatholipidae	1	1	Sparassidae	1	1
Dictynidae	1	1	Theridiidae	8	10
Eresidae	1	1	Thomisidae	9	15
Gnaphosidae	2	2	Trachelidae	2	2
Hahniidae	1	1	Uloboridae	2	2
Linyphiidae	2	2	Zodariidae	1	1
Mimetidae	1	1	Zoropsidae	1	1
Oxyopidae	2	3	Palpimanidae	1	1
			Total 26	75	94

Forty-one species are African endemics, 39 are Southern African endemics, and only eight are South African endemics and nine are near Eastern Cape endemics.

Table 2: Conservation status and endemism of the spider species sampled at Thyspunt (DD—Data deficient; NE—not evaluated; LC—Least Concern)

	No spp.	Code	%
Conservation status			
Data deficient (taxonomic reason or lack distribution data)	3	DD	3.1
Not evaluated (immature, new or undetermined)	8	NE	8.3
Least concern	83	LC	88.3
Vulnerable	0	VU	0
Endemism			
0 – Africa and wider (C)	6	LC	6.3
1 – Africa endemics (AE)	41	LC	43.6
2 – Southern Africa endemics (STHE)	15	LC	15.9
3 – South Africa endemics (SAE): more than three provinces	15	LC	15.9
4 – South Africa endemics (SAE): two adjacent provinces	9	LC/rare	9.6
5 – Eastern Cape endemics (ECE)	0	DD/rare	0
6 – Type locality	0	RARE	0

CONCLUSION

A total of 94 species were newly recorded from Thyspunt. All these data have been incorporated into the Spider Red Listing project. With the ecology and diversity of the spider fauna of South Africa so poorly known, each survey contributes to our knowledge on the geographical distribution of spider species. Although this paper probably represents only a portion of the spider fauna present, we hope this information will stimulate further interest and research.

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Figures 5-19. Spiders from Thyspunt: 5. *Neoscona rufipalpis* (Araneidae); 6. *Ideocaira transversa* (Araneidae); 7. *Acanthepeira* sp. (Araneidae); 8. *Gasteracantha sanguinolenta* (Araneidae); 9. *Gea infuscata* (Araneidae); 10. *Ubcisi capensis* (Cyatholipidae); 11. *Dictyna* sp. (Dictynidae); 12. *Aphantaulax signicollis* (Gnaphosidae); 13. *Hahnia laticeps* (Hahniidae); 14. *Hamataliwa fronticornis* (Oxyopidae); 15. *Palpimanus capensis* (Palpimanidae); 16. Philodromidae (new genus); 17. *Walrencea globosa* (Pisauridae); 18. *Chiasmopes lineatus* (Pisauridae); 19. *Euprosthonopsis pulchella* (Pisauridae). Photo credits: L. Wiese.

Figures 20-34. Spiders from Thyspunt: 20. *Brancus mustelus* (Salticidae); 21. *Myrmarachne laurentina* (Salticidae); 22. *Baryphas ahenus* (Salticidae); 23. *Leucauge thomeensis* (Tetragnathidae); 24. *Argyrodes zonatus* (Theridiidae); 25. *Theridion* sp. (Theridiidae); 26. *Phoroncidia* sp. (Theridiidae); 27. *Rubroridion* sp. (Theridiidae); 28. *Euryopsis funebris* (Theridiidae); 29. *Pherecydes tuberculatus* (Thomisidae); 30. *Synema simoneae* (Thomisidae); 31. *Thomisops pupa* (male) (Thomisidae); 32. *Synema langheldi* (Thomisidae); 33. *Parabomis martini* (Thomisidae); 34. *Philoponella angolensis* (Uloboridae). Photo credits: L. Wiese.

APPENDIX 1: Spiders of Thyspunt, Eastern Cape, listing their endemicity (END), conservation status (CS) and global distribution (DIST), and known sex (F female, M male and B both) * possibly new species.

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	SEX
AMAUROBIIDAE	<i>Chresiona invalida</i> (Simon, 1898)	3	LC	SAE	F
ARANEIDAE	<i>Acanthepeira</i> sp.*		NE		
	<i>Araneus apricus</i> Karsch, 1884	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Caerostris sexcupidata</i> (Fabricius, 1793)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Cyclosa insulana</i> (Costa, 1834)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Cyclosa oculata</i> (Walckenaer, 1802)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Cyphalonotus larvatus</i> (Simon, 1881)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Cyrtophora citricola</i> (Forsskål, 1775)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Gasteracantha sanguinolenta</i> C.L. Koch, 1844	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Gea infuscata</i> Tullgren, 1910	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Hypsosinga holzapfelae</i> (Lessert, 1936)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Ideocaira transversa</i> Simon, 1903	3	LC	SAE	F
	<i>Larinia chloris</i> (Audouin, 1826)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Larinioides</i> sp.		NE		
	<i>Neoscona blondeli</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Neoscona rufipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Prasonica seriata</i> Simon, 1895	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Trichonephila fenestrata</i> Thorell, 1859	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Zygiella x-notata</i> (Clerck, 1757)	0	LC		B
CHEIRACANTHIIDAE	<i>Cheiramiona clavigera</i> (Simon, 1897)	3	LC	SAE	B
CLUBIONIDAE	<i>Clubiona abbajensis</i> Strand, 1906	1	LC		B
	<i>Clubiona sigillata</i> Lawrence, 1952	3	LC	SAE	M
CORINNIDAE	<i>Pronophaea natalica</i> Simon, 1897	3	LC	SAE	B
CYATHOLIPIDAE	<i>Ubacisi capensis</i> (Griswold, 1987)	4	LC	SAE	B
DICTYNIDAE	<i>Dictyna</i> sp.*		NE		
ERESIDAE	<i>Gandanameno spenceri</i> (Pocock, 1900)	2	LC	STHE	B
GNAPHOSIDAE	<i>Aphantaulax signicollis</i> Tucker, 1923	2	LC	STHE	F
	<i>Xerophaeus communis</i> Purcell, 1907	3	LC	SAE	B
HAHNIIDAE	<i>Hahnia laticeps</i> Simon, 1898	3	LC	SAE	F
LINYPHIIDAE	<i>Mecynidis dentipalpis</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	M
	<i>Neriene flammea</i> Van Helsdingen, 1969	4	DD	SAE	M
MIMETIDAE	<i>Ero capensis</i> Simon, 1895	2	LC	STHE	F
OXYOPIIDAE	<i>Hamataliwa fronticornis</i> (Lessert, 1927)	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Oxyopes flavipalpis</i> (Lucas, 1858)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp.*		NE		
PALPIMANIDAE	<i>Palpimanus capensis</i> Simon, 1893	3	LC	SAE	B
PHILODROMIDAE	New genus*		NE		
	<i>Gephyrota glauca</i> (Jézéquel, 1966)	1	LC	AE	B
PISAUROIDAE	<i>Chiasmopes lineatus</i> (Pocock, 1898)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Euprosthenopsis pulchella</i> (Pocock, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Walrencea globosa</i> Blandin, 1979	4	DD	SAE	B
SALTICIDAE	<i>Baryphas ahenus</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Brancus mustelus</i> (Simon, 1902)	2	LC	STHE	M
	<i>Dendryphantas purcelli</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Evarcha denticulata</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2013	4	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Habrocestum laurae</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	4	DD	SAE	F
	<i>Harmochirus luculentus</i> Simon, 1885	1	LC	AE	B

FAMILY	SPECIES	END	CS	DIST	SEX
	<i>Heliophanus hastatus</i> Wesolowska, 1986	1	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Heliophanus modicus</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Hyllus brevitarsis</i> Simon, 1902	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Massagris honesta</i> Wesolowska, 1993	4	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Myrmarachne laurentina</i> Bacelar, 1953	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Rhene lingularis</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	3	LC	SAE	M
	<i>Rhene machadoi</i> Berland & Millot, 1941	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Rhene timidus</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2013	4	LC	SAE	F
	<i>Thyene leighi</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	M
	<i>Thyene natalii</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thyene ogdeni</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1903	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thyene thyenioides</i> (Lessert, 1925)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thyenula juvenca</i> Simon, 1902	3	LC	SAE	B
SCYTODIDAE	<i>Scytodes elizabethae</i> Purcell, 1904	3	LC	SAE	M
SPARASSIDAE	<i>Palystes superciliosus</i> L. Koch, 1875	2	LC	STHE	B
TETRAGNATHIDAE	<i>Leucauge festiva</i> (Blackwall, 1866)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Leucauge thomeensis</i> Kraus, 1960	1	LC	AE	M
THERIDIIDAE	<i>Argyrodes convivans</i> Lawrence, 1937	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Argyrodes zonatus</i> (Walckenaer, 1841)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Episinus bilineatus</i> Simon, 1894	2	LC	STHE	J
	<i>Euryopsis funebris</i> (Hentz, 1850)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	1	LC	C	B
	<i>Phoroncidia</i> sp.*		NE		
	<i>Phycosoma martinae</i> (Roberts, 1983)	0	LC	C	B
	<i>Rubroridion</i> sp.*		NE		
	<i>Theridion purcelli</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1904	3	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Theridion</i> sp.*		NE		
THOMISIDAE	<i>Avelis hystriculus</i> Simon, 1895	3	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Oxytate leruthi</i> (Lessert, 1943)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Parabomis martini</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Pherecydes nicolaasi</i> Dippenaar-Schoeman, 1980	3	LC	SAE	B
	<i>Pherecydes tuberculatus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1883	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Phrynarachne melloleitaoi</i> Lessert, 1933	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Synema imitatrix</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Synema langheldi</i> Dahl, 1907	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Synema nigrotibiale</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	M
	<i>Synema simoneae</i> Lessert, 1919	1	LC	AE	F
	<i>Thomisops pupa</i> Karsch, 1879	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thomisus daradioides</i> Simon, 1890	1	LC	C	B
	<i>Thomisus scrupeus</i> (Simon, 1886)	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	1	LC	AE	B
	<i>Tmarus cameliformis</i> Millot, 1942	1	LC	AE	B
TRACHELIDAE	<i>Afroseto martini</i> (Simon, 1897)	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Thysanina transversa</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	3	LC	SAE	B
ULOBORIDAE	<i>Miagrammopes longicaudus</i> O.P.-Cambridge, 1882	2	LC	STHE	B
	<i>Philoponella angolensis</i> (Lessert, 1933)	1	LC	AE	M
ZODARIIDAE	<i>Chariobas lineatus</i> Pocock, 1900	4	LC	SAE	J
ZOROPSIDAE	<i>Griswoldia urbensis</i> (Lawrence, 1942)	4	LC	SAE	B